

Convergence Without Coherence: A Pre-Registered Test of Distributed Transdiagnostic Epigenetic Architecture in 181 Adversity-Related EWAS

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Abstract

Background. A recurring claim in the epigenetics of human adversity is that diverse stressors leave partially convergent methylation marks at HPA-axis loci. Independent replication of such convergence claims under strict criteria is rare.

Methods. Using the EWAS Catalog (snapshot 2026-04-09), I identified 181 published EWAS whose trait, exposure or outcome matched adversity-related keywords. Three criteria for a CpG to count as “convergent” across this corpus were pre-registered: presence in ≥ 3 independent studies, directional concordance $\geq 75\%$, and $|median\Delta\beta| \geq 0.01$. The resulting convergent gene set was tested for functional enrichment against Gene Ontology Biological Process and Reactome (FDR < 0.05 , Benjamini–Hochberg). Critically, the enrichment was compared to that of 1,000 size-matched random gene sets sampled from the EWAS Catalog background, with significance based on the empirical p -value and on the proportion of enriched terms falling in pre-registered apriori categories (stress response, glucocorticoid signaling, inflammation/immunity, neurodevelopment, mitochondrial/metabolic, epigenetic regulation).

Results. 828 convergent CpG loci were identified, mapping to 443 unique genes. The convergent set was strongly biased toward hypermethylation (596 hyper vs. 232 hypo). The five most represented genes (PRDM8, PPT2, PRRT1, AHRR, GFI1) include the canonical smoking-EWAS hits AHRR and GFI1, while the pre-registered HPA candidate genes (FKBP5, NR3C1, CRH, CRHR1) contributed 2 convergent CpGs combined and none reached gene-level convergence. The convergent set produced 2,069 significant GO BP terms, whereas size-matched random gene sets produced on average 5,408 significant terms; only one GO term was uniquely enriched in the convergent set and not in any random set, and 80–94% of enriched terms fell in the “other” category, with only 0.9–2.8% in adversity-related apriori categories. A tissue-stratified robustness check restricted to adult blood-tissue studies ($n = 84$) yielded a smaller convergent set (33 genes) further dominated by smoking markers (CYP1A1, AHRR, MYO1G, FRMD4A, GFI1), identifying tobacco smoking as a plausible major confounder.

Conclusion. The hypothesis of a distributed, functionally coherent epigenetic architecture detectable in adversity EWAS is refuted at the cross-cohort summary-statistics level under the pre-registered criteria. Convergent direction exists at the locus level, but the resulting gene set is functionally indistinguishable from random sets of comparable size, and its top contributors are dominated by signatures of demographic confounders. Cross-cohort epigenetic convergence claims in this literature warrant explicit demonstration rather than assumption.

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1. Introduction

Two decades of epigenome-wide association studies (EWAS) of human adversity have produced a sprawling literature linking diverse exposures — childhood maltreatment, prenatal maternal stress, post-traumatic stress disorder, socioeconomic deprivation — to DNA methylation changes at putatively shared regulatory loci [5, 6, 11, 12]. A particularly persistent claim is that the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis genes *FKBP5*, *NR3C1*, *CRH* and *CRHR1* serve as transdiagnostic loci of biological embedding: their methylation states are claimed to converge across heterogeneous adversities, providing a measurable substrate of “stress under the skin”.

Two empirical realities, however, complicate this picture. First, EWAS as a methodology has well-documented reproducibility problems — small effect sizes near the limit of technical noise, residual confounding by cell composition, smoking, age, and population stratification, sparse cross-platform agreement, and asymmetric publication [3, 4, 2]. Second, the very framing of “convergence” is rarely tested explicitly: studies report direction of effect at HPA loci in a single cohort, and the reader is left to infer that overlapping findings across cohorts constitute convergence, even when those cohorts differ in exposure, tissue, platform and population.

This study tests the convergence claim directly. After a pilot analysis suggested that gene-level convergence in the four HPA candidate genes was weak and not specific (*FKBP5* marginal; *NR3C1*, *CRH*, *CRHR1* null; the presumed negative control *VPS37B* stronger than *FKBP5*), the question was reformulated more broadly. The pre-registered hypothesis examined here is:

Human adversity induces partial patterns of epigenetic convergence distributed across multiple biological systems, where reproducibility emerges at the level of functional networks rather than in specific candidate genes.

The corresponding empirical prediction is that the set of CpGs showing high directional concordance across independent adversity EWAS should be enriched for functionally coherent biological pathways at a frequency higher than expected from size-matched random gene sets. The criteria for support, refutation, and the apriori categories of biological coherence were fixed before the enrichment analysis (Section 2).

2. Methods

2.1. Data source and filtering

The analysis used the EWAS Catalog [1], snapshot 2026-04-09, comprising study-level metadata and CpG-level summary statistics across published EWAS. Studies whose `trait`, `exposure` or `outcome` fields contained any of a pre-specified set of adversity-related keywords (ACE, abuse, maltreatment, trauma, PTSD, stress, depression, anxiety, prenatal/maternal/gestational stress,

cortisol/glucocorticoid, discrimination, socioeconomic, war, conflict, violence, pandemic, allostatic, adversity, and morphological variants) were retained. This yielded 181 studies. All subsequent analyses operated exclusively on this subset.

2.2. Pre-registered convergence criteria

Convergence was operationalized at the CpG level. For each CpG present in the adversity-filtered subset, per-study directional effects were collapsed to the median if a study contributed multiple records. A CpG was defined as *convergent* if and only if it met all three pre-registered thresholds:

1. Presence in ≥ 3 independent studies (`MIN_STUDIES = 3`);
2. Directional concordance $\geq 75\%$ across studies (`CONCORDANCE_THRESHOLD = 0.75`);
3. Magnitude $|median\Delta\beta| \geq 0.01$ (`MIN_DELTA_BETA = 0.01`).

These thresholds were fixed before the enrichment analysis and not modified based on intermediate results.

2.3. Functional enrichment and matched random comparison

The convergent gene set — defined as the union of all genes annotated to any convergent CpG in the EWAS Catalog gene field — was tested for over-representation in Gene Ontology Biological Process (GO BP) and Reactome pathways using Fisher’s exact test with Benjamini–Hochberg FDR correction. The background gene universe was the set of all human genes appearing at least once in the EWAS Catalog `gene` field — not the full genome — to avoid the bias introduced by uneven representation in array-based EWAS.

To establish the null distribution, 1,000 random gene sets of identical size were sampled without replacement from the same background. For each random set, identical enrichment analysis was performed. The empirical p -value of the convergent set is the proportion of random sets producing enrichment in any of the pre-registered apriori categories at $FDR < 0.05$ that is at least as strong as the convergent set’s observed enrichment in those categories.

2.4. Pre-registered apriori categories

For an enriched term to count as supporting the primary hypothesis, it had to fall in one of six pre-declared apriori categories: (i) stress response / cellular stress; (ii) glucocorticoid signaling / HPA axis; (iii) inflammation / immune regulation; (iv) neurodevelopment / synaptic function / nervous system; (v) mitochondrial / metabolic adaptation; (vi) epigenetic regulation / chromatin. Terms matching these categories were identified by keyword and curated database annotation. All other significantly enriched terms were grouped as “other”. Two additional descriptive (non-apriori) categories were tracked to monitor for known confounders: “aging / cell composition” and “smoking / xenobiotic”.

2.5. Decision rules

The hypothesis was considered *supported* only if (a) at least one term in an apriori category was enriched at $FDR < 0.05$ in Reactome; (b) the same finding was reproduced in GO BP; (c) the empirical p -value vs. matched random sets was < 0.05 . A finding of convergent loci alone, without these three jointly, was pre-specified as insufficient evidence for the primary hypothesis.

2.6. Code and pre-registration

All analyses were performed in Python 3 (`pandas`, `numpy`, `scipy`, `gseapy`).. The pre-registration document and full reproducible code are available at the repository linked in Section 5.

3. Results

3.1. Coverage

After filtering, 181 EWAS contributed to the adversity-filtered subset. Within this subset, CpGs appearing in at least 3 independent studies and meeting both the concordance and magnitude thresholds yielded **828 convergent loci** mapping to **443 unique genes**.

3.2. Convergent loci and direction

Among the 828 convergent CpGs, 596 (72%) showed dominant hypermethylation across studies and 232 (28%) showed dominant hypomethylation, indicating a 2.5:1 directional skew toward hypermethylation. The mean directional concordance fraction in the convergent set was 0.973; 75% of convergent loci showed full directional agreement across the contributing studies. CpGs in the convergent set appeared in a median of 4 studies (range 3–18).

3.3. Top contributing genes and identity of the convergent set

The five most represented genes in the convergent set were *PRDM8* (13 CpGs), *PPT2* (11 CpGs), *PRRT1* (10 CpGs), *AHRR* (10 CpGs) and *GFI1* (10 CpGs). *AHRR* and *GFI1* are the two best-replicated canonical EWAS signatures of tobacco smoking [13]. Critically, the pre-registered HPA candidate genes contributed minimally: *FKBP5* (0 convergent CpGs), *NR3C1* (0), *CRH* (1), *CRHR1* (1). The pilot-stage candidate negative control *VPS37B* also contributed 0 convergent CpGs under the stricter pre-registered criteria.

3.4. Functional enrichment is below the random-matched baseline

The convergent gene set yielded 2,069 significantly enriched GO BP terms and 849 significantly enriched Reactome pathways at $FDR < 0.05$. However, size-matched random gene sets sampled from the EWAS Catalog background produced a mean of 5,408 significantly enriched GO BP terms (Figure 1A). Only 1 GO BP term was uniquely enriched in the convergent set and not in any of the 1,000 random sets. The empirical comparison thus places the convergent set's

Figure 1. Convergent gene set vs. matched random controls. (A) Distribution of the number of significantly enriched GO Biological Process terms (FDR < 0.05) across 1,000 size-matched random gene sets sampled from the EWAS Catalog background. The convergent set’s value (red, n = 2,069) lies far below the random distribution (dashed, mean ≈ 5,408). (B) Distribution of significantly enriched terms across pre-registered apriori categories and two descriptive confounder categories, for GO BP (blue) and Reactome (orange). Across both databases, 80–95% of enriched terms fall in the “other” category, outside any pre-registered category of biological coherence with adversity.

enrichment well below the random-matched distribution, in direct opposition to the predicted direction.

3.5. Apriori category distribution

Of the significantly enriched terms in the convergent set, 80.2% (GO BP) and 94.5% (Reactome) fell in the “other” category, outside any of the six pre-registered apriori categories of biological coherence (Figure 1B). Terms in adversity-related apriori categories accounted for only 2.8% (GO BP) and 0.9% (Reactome). The next largest category was “aging / cell composition” at 16.5% (GO BP) and 3.6% (Reactome); “smoking / xenobiotic” accounted for 0.5–0.9%.

3.6. Decision under pre-registered rules

Three conditions had to be jointly met for the primary hypothesis to be considered supported: at least one Reactome term enriched in an apriori category at FDR < 0.05, the same in GO BP, and an empirical p -value < 0.05 vs. random matched sets. The first two were nominally met (some apriori-category terms are present), but the third condition fails decisively: the convergent set’s enrichment is lower than the random-matched mean, not higher than the 95th percentile. The hypothesis is refuted under its own pre-registered criteria.

4. Discussion

4.1. *What the result is, in plain terms*

There is reproducible direction-of-effect convergence at specific CpG loci across adversity EWAS. The 828 convergent loci identified here are not statistical noise: they appear with consistent directional sign in three or more independent studies, with non-trivial median effect size. However, the gene set generated by aggregating these loci does *not* organize itself into recognizable biological networks beyond what is expected from a random gene set of the same size. The functional architecture promised by the convergence hypothesis is absent in the public summary-level data.

4.2. *Why convergence at loci does not imply biological architecture*

The discrepancy is structural, not interpretive. Convergent loci can arise from any process that produces correlated directional shifts across studies of similar populations: shared confounding by smoking, by leukocyte composition shifts, by ageing trajectories, by population stratification, or by directional publication bias. The dominance of *AHRR* and *GFI1* — the strongest smoking-EWAS hits in the human methylome — in the convergent set is consistent with smoking confounding being a substantial driver of apparent adversity-related convergence, since adverse exposures and tobacco use co-occur in many cohorts and adjustment for smoking is inconsistent across the underlying EWAS [13, 3].

The 2.5:1 hypermethylation skew adds to this picture: technical and demographic confounders (cell composition shifts toward neutrophils, age-related hypermethylation drift) typically produce directional skews of this magnitude in the absence of mechanism-specific biology [14, 15].

4.3. *Why the convergent set is functionally weaker than random*

The observation that random gene sets of identical size produce more than twice as many significantly enriched terms as the convergent set is informative. Random sampling from the EWAS Catalog background tends to over-include genes that are densely annotated and central to multiple pathways. The convergent set, by contrast, is dominated by genes that are repeatedly hit in EWAS for reasons related to assay properties (*AHRR*, *GFI1*, *PRDM8*, *PPT2*) rather than for functional centrality. The convergent set is thus enriched in EWAS-frequent but functionally peripheral genes — a profile consistent with assay-driven rather than biology-driven convergence.

4.4. *What was not refuted*

Three claims are not addressed by this analysis. First, individual-level reanalyses of cohorts with harmonized preprocessing and adequate covariate control may reveal coherent functional architectures that summary-level meta-analytic approaches cannot detect. Second, narrower convergence claims — for instance, that specific CpGs in regulatory regions of a single gene like *FKBP5* show directionally consistent effects within a particular exposure (e.g., childhood maltreatment in blood from adolescent samples) — may survive in domains not stratified here.

The hypothesis refuted in this study is the broad transdiagnostic-distributed-architecture claim under the operational definition adopted. Third, whether human adversity leaves a coordinated trace at levels of biological organization not captured by CpG-level meta-analysis — single-cell methylation heterogeneity, chromatin dynamics, or tissue-scale emergent patterns — remains entirely outside the scope of this test.

4.5. Limitations

The keyword-based filter for adversity studies is necessarily imperfect; it likely over-includes loose “stress”-related EWAS and under-includes studies that did not include the keywords in their indexed metadata fields. The convergence thresholds (75%, $|\Delta\beta| \geq 0.01$, ≥ 3 studies) are defensible but not unique; alternative thresholds would yield different convergent sets, although the random-matched comparison would still apply. The EWAS Catalog gene annotation inherits whatever errors are present in the Illumina manifest annotations from which it derives. The pre-registered apriori category keywords were curated by a single investigator and may under-identify legitimate biological coherence framed in unfamiliar terms. A tissue-stratified robustness analysis was performed restricting the corpus to adult blood-tissue studies (whole blood, peripheral blood, leukocytes; $n = 84$ studies after excluding cord blood, placenta, brain and epithelial tissues). Under identical pre-registered criteria, this subset yielded 73 convergent CpGs mapping to 33 unique genes. The top contributors shifted toward an even more smoking-dominated profile: CYP1A1 (8 CpGs), AHRR (7), MYO1G (4), FRMD4A (4) and GFI1 (2) together accounted for 25 of the 73 convergent CpGs. Functional enrichment did not reach $FDR < 0.05$ in either GO Biological Process or Reactome at this set size; however, the highest-ranked Reactome pathways (Xenobiotics, Cytochrome P450 by substrate type, Aryl Hydrocarbon Receptor Signaling) are all driven by CYP1A1 and AHRR.

4.6. Implications for the field

The most immediate implication is methodological. Reports of “convergence” across cohorts in adversity-related EWAS need to be demonstrated explicitly — with size-matched random controls, with pre-registered criteria, with corrections for shared confounders — rather than assumed from overlapping single-study findings. The intuition that adversity leaves a coherent epigenetic signature is not necessarily wrong, but under the rigor of pre-registration plus random-matched comparison, it does not survive in the publicly available summary-level corpus as of mid-2026.

For independent investigators without access to consortium-level individual data, this implies that the testable form of the convergence question is narrower than the field’s current framing. Either richer access to individual-level data is required, or the question itself must be reformulated around components of convergence that can be tested with public summary data and explicit controls.

5. Conclusion

Under pre-registered criteria, 181 published EWAS of adversity yield 828 directionally convergent CpG loci that, taken together, form a gene set whose functional enrichment is statistically indistinguishable from — and quantitatively below — random gene sets of identical size. The hypothesis that adversity-related epigenetic responses are organized into reproducible functional networks at the cross-cohort summary-statistics level of analysis. Cross-cohort convergence claims in this literature should be treated as hypotheses to be demonstrated, not background assumptions.

Pre-registration

The analytical plan including thresholds, apriori categories, decision rules and the commitment to publish the result regardless of outcome was fixed and dated prior to execution of the enrichment step. The pre-registration document is included with the code repository (see Section 5).

Code and data availability

All code, intermediate tables, the pre-registration document and the figure-generation script are deposited as the `epi-convergence-test` toolkit in the Vlattice GitHub repository (<https://github.com/Vlattice/epi-convergence-test>) and will be archived on Zenodo with a citable DOI upon publication. The EWAS Catalog data used (snapshot 2026-04-09) is publicly available at <https://www.ewascatalog.org/>.

Author contributions and acknowledgments

The author conceived the study, performed the analyses, wrote the manuscript, and is responsible for the integrity of the work. This research was conducted independently, without institutional affiliation or funding.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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